

**The Architecture of Emotion: Subjective Realism as a Narrative
Framework for Perceptual and Temporal Fluidity**

Aura Biru

aura.b@mail.com

Abstract

This essay introduces and explores Subjective Realism as a novel narrative framework that reinterprets the relation between emotion, perception, and reality in literature. Grounded in theoretical analysis and applied in literary fiction, the model addresses limitations in conventional narrative forms by demonstrating that the written word can authentically translate emotional and psychological experiences into perceptual realities.

Subjective Realism draws on phenomenology¹, postmodern epistemology², and literary theory³, rejecting a static world in favor of a fluid reality where emotions modulate external perceptions. In this way, the concept departs from both Psychological Realism and Magical Realism, offering a middle ground that places sensory and temporal fluidity at the forefront of narrative construction while remaining grounded and psychologically plausible.

The outlined methodology reveals how the external world becomes mutable in response to the subjective inner life. It highlights the ability to manipulate time, space, and language to reshape perceptual experience by way of distinct strategies such as affective sensory modulation, emotional synesthesia, and temporal elasticity. Additionally, techniques like perceptual degradation, object emotion resonance, and emotional gravitation are examined to illustrate how characters' internal emotional truths prompt readers to reconsider the relationship between perception and reality within the literary context.

In doing so, Subjective Realism contributes to the expansion of narrative theory, offering a comprehensive framework for understanding and embodying emotion in literature.

¹ Maurice Merleau-Ponty, *Phenomenology of Perception* (2002).

² Jean-François Lyotard, *The Postmodern condition: a Report on Knowledge* (1984).

³ Jonathan D. Culler, *Literary Theory: a Very Short Introduction* (2011).

Keywords: Subjective Realism, Narrative Framework, Emotion and Perception, Perceptual Fluidity, Temporal Fluidity, Phenomenology

1. Introduction

The concept of reality in narrative fiction has long been a contested topic, with the division between external experience and internal perception constantly negotiated⁴. Yet, the question of how emotions shape perception remains both compelling and underexplored.⁵

Conventional realism⁶ upholds an objective standard of reality, independent of individual emotional flux. Psychological Realism, for instance, builds on the empirical tradition⁷ by prioritizing believable portrayals of internal experiences, aligning characters' emotional lives with observable reality. Magical Realism⁸ pushes this inquiry further, introducing the fantastical to allow for overt alterations in perception. While both approaches serve their purpose, neither fully captures how emotional states influence and modulate the external world within the perceptual and cognitive dimensions of human experience.

Subjective Realism introduces a new perspective, proposing that emotional and psychological states shape the way reality is experienced⁹. In this framework, perception is not neutral but fluid, adjusting in response to characters' internal lives. Where psychological realism focuses on consciousness and magical realism introduces external fantasy, subjective realism offers a dynamic process in which emotions reshape perception within the bounds of a realistic world, placing sensory fluidity at its core.

⁴ Merleau-Ponty, *Phenomenology of Perception*.

⁵ Jaak Panksepp, *Affective neuroscience : the foundations of human and animal emotions* (1998).

⁶ Ian Watt, *The Rise of the Novel* (1959).

⁷ Dorrit Cohn, *Transparent minds : narrative modes for presenting consciousness in fiction* (2011).

⁸ Maggie Ann Bowers, *Magic(al) Realism* (2004).

⁹ Jean-Paul Sartre, *Being and nothingness : a phenomenological essay on ontology* (1999).

Rooted in phenomenological insights¹⁰ and postmodern epistemology's rejection of objective reality¹¹, subjective realism asserts that all experience is mediated by personal perception. Within this model, time and space are rendered malleable by characters' internal worlds, with temporal shifts and sensory modulation reflecting emotional states.

Several core strategies underpin this approach: affective sensory modulation, where emotions reshape sensory inputs; emotional synesthesia, the blending of affect and perception¹²; and temporal elasticity, where time is perceived nonlinearly, shaped by the intensity of experience¹³.

The narrative framework explored in this essay is demonstrated through practical applications, exemplified by direct excerpts from the forthcoming novel "We Are Everyone" (publication pending), where subjective realism centrally shapes both structure and themes.

¹⁰ Merleau-Ponty, *Phenomenology of Perception*.

¹¹ Lyotard, *The Postmodern condition: a Report on Knowledge*.

¹² Richard E. Cytowic, *The man who tasted shapes* (2003).

¹³ Henri Bergson, *Time and free will : an essay on the immediate data of consciousness* (1910).

2. Theoretical Foundations

2.1 Defining Terms

Subjective Realism

Subjective Realism presents a narrative framework in which the psychological and emotional states of characters directly mediate their experience of reality. The concept operates on the premise that objective reality, though stable, shifts in response to subjective experience, particularly through emotional intensity and psychological fluctuation. The central principle is that reality is not static. Unlike traditional realism, where the external world remains fixed within its limits, Subjective Realism treats perception as a dynamic force that reshapes external reality to reflect internal states. In other words, it implies a rejection of the objective world as fixed. Reality in Subjective Realism is inherently personal, shaped by characters' emotional significance and interpretation of their experiences.

Key Characteristics of Subjective Realism:

- **Emotion-Driven Alterations to Reality:** Sensory perceptions and spatial experiences are reshaped by internal states.
- **Evolving Perception-Based Distortion:** Maintains a realist framework but emphasizes emotional subjectivity, offering an evolving distortion of the world based on perception.
- **Emotional Truth Supersedes Objective Fact:** Emotional truth becomes the lens through which reality is both experienced and communicated to the reader.

Perception

In Subjective Realism, perception functions as an active and dynamic process through which characters interpret and experience reality, profoundly influenced by emotional and psychological states

Emotional Synesthesia

This concept describes how emotions filter sensory perception, transforming how characters experience sensory inputs such as light, sound, and space, blending affect and perception.

2.2 Conceptual Lineage and Divergence

Subjective Realism builds on the foundations of literary fiction¹⁴, psychological realism¹⁵, phenomenology¹⁶, and magical realism¹⁷, while asserting its own distinct position by emphasizing the mutability of reality as filtered through emotional and psychological experience.

2.2.1 Literary Fiction

- **Influence:** Draws from literary fiction's engagement with complex emotional landscapes and a character-driven focus¹⁸.
- **Divergence:** In contrast to the typical separation between inner life and external world, Subjective Realism allows the external world to be dynamically reshaped by the protagonist's emotional state, creating a narrative space that is emotionally adaptive rather than static
- **Key Mechanism:** The environment perceptually shifts in direct correlation to the character's emotional state, generating a world that is emotionally refractive rather than detached.

¹⁴ Stephen Hazell, "Henry James: The Art of Fiction (1884)," (2022).

¹⁵ Fyodor Dostoyevsky, *Notes from the Underground* (2015).

¹⁶ Merleau-Ponty, *Phenomenology of Perception*.

¹⁷ Bowers, *Magic(al) Realism*.

¹⁸ Hazell, "Henry James: The Art of Fiction (1884)."

2.2.2 Psychological Realism

- **Influence:** Extends psychological realism's focus on internal consciousness and subjective interpretations of the world¹⁹.
- **Divergence:** Departs from psychological realism by granting characters' internal states the power to transform sensory perception.
- **Key Mechanism:** Reality itself becomes perceptually mutable, shaped by the psychological dynamics of the character, collapsing the boundary between the internal and external.

2.2.3 Phenomenology

- **Influence:** Incorporates phenomenology's principle of intentionality, where perception is inherently shaped by the perceiver's subjectivity.
- **Divergence:** Moves beyond phenomenology's descriptive mode by introducing emotional cognition as an active force that reshapes perceptual reality.
- **Key Mechanism:** Emotional intensity alters the sensory architecture of reality, where the character's emotional state constructs the perceptual world, shifting it in real time.

2.2.4 Magical Realism

- **Influence:** Mirrors magical realism's subversion of fixed reality²⁰, where the ordinary and extraordinary coexist fluidly.

Divergence: Avoids the supernatural or fantastical elements typical of magical realism, instead allowing psychological plausibility to account for perceptual fluidity.

¹⁹ Dostoyevsky, *Notes from the Underground*.

²⁰ Bowers, *Magic(al) Realism*.

- **Key Mechanism:** Perception is bent by the character's psychological framework, maintaining adherence to realism while embracing perceptual elasticity.

2.3 Broader Philosophical Perspectives

Subjective Realism places particular emphasis on the mutability of perception under the weight of psychological and emotional pressures. It engages with several philosophical concepts:

2.3.1 Bergson's Duration

Subjective Realism aligns with Henri Bergson's concept of duration²¹, where time is experienced as qualitative rather than quantitative. Time, in this narrative framework, becomes an emotionally contingent construct. Characters experience prolonged moments when in distress or rapid temporal acceleration during moments of elation or intense focus, where the felt sense of time overtakes its objective passage, situating temporality within their emotional.

2.3.2 Merleau-Ponty's Embodiment

Maurice Merleau-Ponty's philosophy emphasizes that perception is inherently tied to our bodily existence²². Subjective Realism situates sensory distortions as extensions of embodied emotional experience. Emotions are not abstract states but are experienced physically, affecting how characters interact with and perceive their environment, making the surrounding atmosphere an extension of the psychological environment.

2.3.3 Postmodern Epistemology

Acknowledging the mediation of reality through individual perception and experience, Subjective Realism aligns with postmodern epistemology, which rejects the notion of a singular,

²¹ Bergson, *Time and free will : an essay on the immediate data of consciousness*.

²² Merleau-Ponty, *Phenomenology of Perception*.

objective truth. Instead, it presents the world as a fluid construct, shaped by both internal and external forces—ultimately creating a connection between facts and experience. The emotional state of the character becomes the primary mode of engagement with reality superseding objective facts.

2.4 Enriching Contexts of Subjective Realism

2.4.1 Embodiment

Embodiment lies at the heart of Subjective Realism, positioning perception as inherently tied to the physical body rather than a detached cognitive existence²³. Emotional states take on physical form, altering sensory perceptions in real-time and aligning with phenomenological views on the body's role in shaping experience.

In Subjective Realism, characters' emotions are experienced both mentally and physically, influencing how they interact with their environment. Anxiety, for instance, may present as a tightening in the chest, altering the character's perception of space to feel more confined

2.4.2 Consciousness as Active

Informed by phenomenology, Subjective Realism treats consciousness as a dynamic force actively shaping reality. It operates in contrast with passive models of perception by positioning characters as co-creators of their experiential world. Rather than passive recipients of sensory information, they construct their reality through their emotional and psychological states.

²³ Sartre, *Being and nothingness : a phenomenological essay on ontology*.

3. Methodology

3.1 Core Mechanisms of Subjective Realism

3.1.1 Emotional Synesthesia

This serves as the primary mechanism through which affective states transmute into perceptual distortions. In Subjective Realism, emotions are not confined to internal monologues or reflections but actively modulate sensory input²⁴. Light, sound, texture, and spatial relationships extend the emotional register, creating a sensory map of the mind.

The mechanism mirrors the neurological concept of synesthesia, where sensory modalities merge. In narrative terms, it links sensory and emotional experiences, transforming emotions into tangible sensory realities without breaching plausibility, reinforcing the subjectivity of experience.

3.1.2 Temporal Elasticity

"Subjective Realism repositions time as an emotionally contingent construct, where time expands or contracts based on the emotional intensity of the moment. The relationship between emotion and time is generative rather than reflective, where the emotional state of a character reshapes the perception of temporal flow. This temporal experience

The lived experience of time in this form aligns with Bergsonian duration²⁵, distinguishing psychological time from chronological time and supporting experimental narratives where temporality mirrors emotional intensity.

²⁴ Cytowic, *The man who tasted shapes*.

²⁵ Henri Bergson, *Time and Free Will* (2014).

3.1.3 Subtle Narrative Unreliability

In Subjective Realism, unreliability does not stem from deliberate narrative deception²⁶ but emerges from the emotionally mediated nature of reality. The narrative remains grounded in realism, yet it introduces an inherent tension between perception and objectivity, inviting readers to navigate the perceptual gaps between what is emotionally real for the character and what might be objectively true.

In this way, unreliability is reframed: rather than distorting events through conscious manipulation, perceptions are shaped by emotional distortion, taking precedence over objective fact.

3.1.4 Psychological Atmosphere

Subjective Realism treats space and environment as extensions of a character's inner world²⁷, where the architecture of a scene reflects emotional resonance. The spatial perception of a character—whether a room feels vast or claustrophobic, inviting or hostile—becomes a direct reflection of their internal state.

In subtly altering the atmosphere of physical spaces, it draws the reader into a space where psychological and physical worlds are inextricably intertwined. The result is a narrative form where emotion shapes architecture, and architecture, in turn, reinforces emotional states.

3.1.5 Defamiliarization

Subjective Realism employs defamiliarization to unsettle the reader's perception of everyday objects and spaces. Drawing from Viktor Shklovsky's concept of *ostranenie*

²⁶ Wayne C. Booth, *The rhetoric of fiction* (1961).

²⁷ Gaston Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space* (2014).

(estrangement)²⁸, it renders familiar objects and settings strange and unfamiliar through subjective perception, reinforcing the idea that reality is always mediated, never fully objective, and constantly refracted through emotional experience.

3.1.6 Stream of Perception:

Stream of Perception expands upon the stream of consciousness technique²⁹ by integrating the internal flow of thoughts with external sensory experience. Instead of capturing only the mental experience, Subjective Realism allows thoughts and perceptions to actively alter the character's sensory reality. This blurring between internal consciousness and external reality renders their boundaries fluid and debatable, as the character's inner states shape sensory experiences.

²⁸ Viktor Shklovsky, "Art as Technique," (2020).

²⁹ Cohn, *Transparent minds : narrative modes for presenting consciousness in fiction*.

3.2 Signature Techniques

Subjective Realism incorporates a variety of narrative techniques that empower characters to shape their reality through emotional states. Below are categorized examples illustrating these techniques in practice.

Category 1: Emotional Distortion of Perception

3.2.1 Affective Sensory Modulation (*Emotional Synesthesia*)

Description:

A technique where the character's emotional state directly modulates sensory perception (e.g., light, sound, weight). Emotions alter the sensory experience of the world in a subjectively realistic way, blending senses with feelings³⁰.

Excerpt from the Novel:

The air hangs heavy, thick and tangled in a scent of apathy, lavender, and decay—it wraps around me in comfort and ruin entwined. With each movement, weighted, the ground shifts; sighs under the burden of time.

Analysis:

- **Olfactory Blending:** Emotional states are conveyed through scent, tying apathy, lavender, and decay to her feelings.
- **Tactile and Visual Shifts:** The air and ground reflect emotional weight, as they wrap and shift in response to her inner state.
- **Emotional Duality:** The combination of comfort and ruin entwined captures the contrast of conflicting emotions.

³⁰ Cytowic, *The man who tasted shapes*.

3.2.3 *Perceptual Degradation through Emotional Strain (Perceptual Erosion)*

Description:

A progressive degradation of sensory clarity as emotions overwhelm the character. Intense emotional strain leads to a blurred or distorted perception of the external world, indicating the erosion of the character's grip on their surroundings.

Excerpt from the Novel:

Before me, the hallway. Or some vaguely familiar version of a corridor, now stretching longer than logic allows, shifting into a passage lined with doors of all shapes and sizes; each one whispering secrets, secrets that fear whispers.

Analysis:

- **Spatial Distortion:** The hallway expands unnaturally, mirroring the character's emotional tension.
- **Auditory Hallucination:** Doors whisper secrets, giving her fears a voice through external elements.
- **Unfamiliar Familiarity:** The corridor's ambiguous nature deepens the sense of unease, amplifying her disconnection from reality.

3.2.4 *Emotional Afterimages*

Description:

Emotional experiences leave lingering sensory impressions, or "*afterimages*," on the character's perception. These are residual effects where past emotions momentarily alter current sensory input³¹, causing the character to perceive echoes of previous sensations.

³¹ Oliver Sacks, *Hallucinations* (2012).

Excerpt from the Novel:

I turn the lever; a faint creak, followed by heavy silence—then, an accelerating gurgle. The stream gushes out, but instead of water, screams burst from the pipes. They are all mine. All the voices I've shut inside for so long start pouring out louder than anything I could perform. I can't cover my ears and block them out. They are screaming at me from the inside, in unstoppable, eerily mind-fucking volumes, telling me to realize what's happening. Forcing me to face my pain.

Analysis:

- **Residual Emotional Impact:** Screams serve as echoes of past trauma surfacing in the present.
- **Sensory Distortion:** Water is perceived as screams, reflecting the intensity of her emotional state.
- **Emotional Echoes:** The line between past and present blurs as emotions from the past reemerge, altering her current perception.

3.2.5 Emotional Centripetal Focus (Emotional Vortex)

Description:

A technique that draws all narrative elements toward a singular emotional core³². Intense emotions create a vortex effect that pulls surrounding aspects of reality inward, concentrating the plot on one emotional truth.

Excerpt from the Novel (Core Emotional Vortex):

His lips, caught mid-thought, stuttered to silence as I rose on my toes, cutting off whatever half-formed sentence had lingered between us with the only response that mattered: the touch of 'yes.' All the 'if-lys' and 'maybe-somedays' we'd ever entertained summed up and exhaled in a kiss. The world didn't so much disappear as it contracted to

³² Panksepp, *Affective neuroscience : the foundations of human and animal emotions*.

a single, suspended heartbeat, where everything else—noise, movement, time itself—bled into a peripheral blur.

Analysis:

- **Temporal Contraction:** Time collapses to a “*suspended heartbeat*,” reflecting how emotions shape the narrative around a singular moment.
- **Sensory Blurring:** The external world dissolves into a blur, reinforcing the dominance of the emotional experience.
- **Language Transformed into Action:** The kiss becomes the only necessary expression, replacing words and thoughts with physical connection.

Category 2: Time and Memory

3.2.6 Temporal Elasticity

Description:

Time becomes emotionally subjective. Characters might experience prolonged moments during distress or rapid acceleration during elation. Temporality is fluid, shaped by the character’s emotional and psychological state, making the experience of time nonlinear³³.

Excerpt from the Novel:

Time stretched itself thin, aware of its own importance, teasing the edges of eternity just enough for my instant to feel endless.

Analysis:

- **Personification of Time:** Time is described as being “*aware*” and “*teasing*,” reflecting a subjective interpretation rather than an objective measure.

³³ Bergson, *Time and free will : an essay on the immediate data of consciousness*.

- **Temporal Distortion:** Moments feel prolonged under emotional influence, making time seem both significant and endless.
- **Emotional Influence:** Anticipation heightens the subjective experience of time, reshaping how moments are perceived.

3.2.7 *Temporal Grief Looping*

Description:

Unresolved emotions from the past repeatedly echo in the present, causing the character to relive significant moments. In narrative, these loops structure a cyclical experience of time, where past and present blend³⁴ under emotional resonance.

Excerpt from the Novel:

6 a.m. January. Still heavy with night. The street had been empty. Slick cobblestones, with a thin sheen of dew; a lingering yawn, spun from the dark and the sea. We were waiting for something—the light, maybe. The day hadn't come yet, but it was close. So close. You could feel it. I felt it. I feel all of it.

Analysis:

- **Recurrent Memory:** The recollection of the moment intrudes on the present, collapsing temporal boundaries.
- **Emotional Echo:** The memory evokes the emotions felt during the original moment, making the past feel immediate and present.
- **Impact on Present Reality:** Past and present experiences blend, creating a distorted perception of time shaped by emotional resonance.

³⁴ Sigmund Freud, *On Murder, Mourning and Melancholia* - Freud (2024).

3.2.8 Active Temporal Recontextualization (Memory as Living Force)

Description:

Memory is treated as an active agent that continuously recontextualizes the present³⁵.

Recollections dynamically shape current perceptions and interactions, making the past a living force in the character's current reality.

Excerpt from the Novel:

Every time I think back to our December, the details blur and sharpen in turns. After scores of seconds or decades now slogging through the wreckage of my mind, I can't help but wonder: is memory the story we tell ourselves or the story we wish it had been?

Analysis:

- **Dynamic Memory:** Memories actively influence how the character perceives the present.
- **Questioning Reality:** The nature of memory becomes uncertain, suggesting that subjective reality is shaped between what was and what is.
- **Living Past:** The past interacts with the present as an active, dynamic force, continuously recontextualizing experience.

3.2.9 Psychological Temporal Fragmentation (Internal Monologue as Temporal Dislocation)

Description:

Internal monologue fragments time, allowing the simultaneous processing of past, present, and future emotional states. It reflects complex psychological processing by distorting the linear progression of time within the character's mind³⁶.

³⁵ Paul Ricoeur, *Memory, History, Forgetting* (2009).

³⁶ Cohn, *Transparent minds : narrative modes for presenting consciousness in fiction*.

Excerpt from the Novel:

The character narrates, “I thought. I felt. I struggled. I...” while, in parallel, her inner monologue intrudes with overwhelming sensations: “*My knees get weaker. Breath stops. I... Am almost there. I... Am consumed. I...*”. The blend of narration and internal monologue here fragments the perception of time, blurring the line between thought and experience.

Analysis:

- **Temporal Fragmentation:** The simultaneous narration and inner monologue reflect the collapse of distinct timeframes into one.
- **Disrupted Linear Progression:** The interjection of internal thoughts disturbs the sequential flow of time.
- **Emotional Overload:** The emotional weight of the scene causes temporal dislocation, distorting the character’s perception of self and surroundings.

3.2.10 The Dissolving Present

Description:

The present moment becomes fluid, constantly dissolving into memories or future anxieties. Characters are unable to live fully in the now because time is unstable, always slipping away due to emotional turmoil.

Excerpt from the Novel:

One last attempt at balance—I clutch onto the cushions, sliding my fingers across the fabric in a graze, rough and familiar, like braille pages of our past, inviting touch to read our history. It speaks of nights spent searching for meanings and mornings meant for finding peace. My body sinks into its enveloping emptiness, grounding myself in the present as it’s pulling me deeper into the past. The touch of the tactile recalls the moments that built us, brushing them against my skin.

Analysis:

- **Blurring of Time:** Touching the cushions triggers memories, altering the present moment.
- **Sensory Triggers:** The rough fabric evokes vivid memories, dissolving the boundary between past and present.
- **Emotional Weight:** The inability to stay grounded reflects emotional turmoil, causing the present dissolves into memory under stress.

3.2.11 Inverted Temporal Affectivity (Temporal Emotional Inversion)

Description:

Emotions are dislocated from their expected timeframes, causing characters to experience feelings like grief, joy, or anger in reverse or unexpected temporal contexts—such as grieving a future event or reliving past joy with fresh intensity.

Excerpt from the Novel:

Anticipation and anxiety tangled tighter together, spiraling into some euphoric mix of hope and fear—like the split second before a leap, where you're not sure if you'll fall or fly, but you're already in mid-air, grinning at the sheer audacity of it.

Analysis:

- **Future Grief:** The anticipation of future outcomes causes present anxiety, blending emotions across time.
- **Emotional Dislocation:** Emotions appear outside of their usual temporal boundaries, with fear and hope intertwining.
- **Inversion of Expectation:** Joy and fear coexist, reflecting the disruption of emotional norms through temporal displacement.

Category 3: Language and Dialogue

3.2.12 Linguistic Decomposition under Emotional Stress

Description:

Language progressively decomposes as the character's emotions escalate, leading to fragmented or incomplete speech³⁷. The gradual erosion signals the breakdown of verbal coherence under the weight of intense emotional experience.

Excerpt from the Novel:

Note: The visual structure of this excerpt, as well as changes in punctuation, reflect the breakdown of language under emotional stress, which is central to the concept of linguistic decomposition.

“It’s not like this. I can’t... I just— I don’t know how to move from here. Something’s wrong, but it’s not me, not just me.

‘Shadow, can you—’”

I break off, unsure of what I’m even asking. I’m not sure what I need.

Something.

Anything.

What is happening?

*The shadow exhales and all I can make out is a faint
like*

it’s vanishing—

“I don’t know either.”

—into the air between us, and even that tone is being pulledddd.

For the first time, I hear something in its voice that doesn’t belong. A hesitation.

A question.

³⁷ R. D. Laing, *The divided self: an existential study in sanity and madness* (1960).

Something new.

A faint, final flicker fades, and—

'Breathe...'

—and the sound finished, too.

...

There is nothing left.

.

.

.

The Void hums.

It was always there. Always here.

Always waiting.

.

And now, we're at the center:

The pointless

point

of no return.

.

"Shadow, what do I do now?

What's next?"

It doesn't react but...

'You hear me, you feel me...

Don't you?'

It turns to me pallid, dimming from within.

"Sha..."

In a sharp,

shared

gasp for air,

it cuts me off

and—

— "Aura?"

What now?"

"I can't continue.

I can't

do

th

i

s"

I wait for the next word. But nothing comes

Analysis:

- **Syntax Breakdown:** Sentences fragment, and words are spaced irregularly mirroring the collapse of coherent thought under intense emotional pressure.
- **Ellipses and Pauses:** The increasing use of ellipses and isolated lines slows the rhythm, pointing at the struggle to communicate.
- **Direct Address to the Author:** Characters break the fourth wall, blurring boundaries between narrative and reality.
- **Emotional Intensity:** The Void's transformation symbolizes the overwhelming pull of depression.

3.2.13 Linguistic Sculpting of Memory

Description:

Memory becomes malleable and is reshaped by the language used to describe it. As a character recalls an event, the language they choose actively alters the memory itself³⁸, making the past a living, changing entity.

³⁸ Elizabeth F. Loftus, *Memory, Surprising New Insights Into how We Remember and why We Forget* (1980).

Excerpt from the Novel:

Included under the analysis of "Every time I think back to our December..."

Analysis:

- **Fluctuating Clarity:** Language causes details to "*blur and sharpen.*"
- **Active Reconstruction:** The act of narration reshapes the memory.
- **Subjective Reality:** Memory is influenced by present emotions and language.

3.2.14 Dynamic Metaphoric Evolution (Metaphor Morphing)

Description:

Metaphors are not static but evolve in response to a character's emotional or psychological development³⁹. They gradually change in meaning or form to reflect the shifting perceptions and frame of mind as the narrative progresses.

Excerpt from the Novel:

*A central metaphor throughout the narrative, **the comet** initially embodies hope and reassurance, shared between the protagonist and her partner. It further transforms into the symbol of destruction, marking their breakup, with its aftermath reflecting the protagonist's emotional instability. In Chapter 2, the comet is personified, representing her attempt to bargain and prevent the tragedy from happening in the first place. As she progresses through grief, the comet evolves into a symbol of reflection and eventual renewal, marking both closure and the potential of new beginnings.*

Analysis:

- **Evolving Symbols:** The comet shifts from a hopeful metaphor to one of emotional devastation, then becomes a symbol of reflection and renewal.

³⁹ George Lakoff and Mark Johnson, *Metaphors we live by* (1980).

- **Reflective Metaphors:** The comet’s personification highlights significance, allowing the protagonist to interact with it as part of her inner journey.
- **Emotional Alignment:** The metaphor’s transformation mirrors the protagonist’s emotional trajectory, marking milestones in her grieving and healing process.

3.2.15 Layered Dualities in Dialogue (Dual-Layered Dialogue)

Description:

Characters convey conflicting emotional truths simultaneously. While the surface conversation communicates one emotion, the underlying subtext or tone reflects a contrasting, often contradictory, feeling. It is a multilayered emotional depiction, as both dialogue levels work together to reveal the characters' vulnerabilities and internal conflict.

Excerpt from the Novel:

So, the lines began to blur.

‘What if all the rain fell down at once?’ Our chats flirted with the surreal, sometimes tipping over into it entirely. We wove wonder into words, opened doors to places we hadn’t dared to go before. Then—surely, subtly—we watched as the walls we built ourselves in began to crumble, like they were always meant to.

Analysis:

- **Surface vs. Subtext:** conversations conceal deeper feelings, creating a contrast between what is said and what is felt.
- **Emotional Duality:** Playful words express both a longing for connection and the discomfort of opening up emotionally.
- **Unspoken Understanding:** The characters share an implicit awareness of their growing intimacy, conveyed through subtext rather than direct statements.

3.2.16 Meta-Emotional Inversion

Description:

Characters experience opposing emotional truths simultaneously, creating a duality where conflicting meanings coexist. The technique explores emotional paradoxes, reshaping characters' perceptions and inviting readers to engage with these contrasts as concurrent realities.

Excerpt from the Novel:

Booking that flight was like placing a bet I knew I wouldn't win, hoping for a miracle but prepared for the inevitable. Here's the catch: I wasn't sure which outcome I was rooting for—whether the miracle was in winning, losing, or something in between. And in-between I wandered, carried by clouds and sedated apprehension. My predicament, however, defiantly pursued its devious descent. Anticipation and anxiety tangled tighter together, spiraling into some euphoric mix of hope and fear—like the split second before a leap, where you're not sure if you'll fall or fly, but you're already in mid-air, grinning at the sheer audacity of it.

Analysis:

- **Duality of Emotions:** The protagonist hopes for a miracle while simultaneously preparing for defeat, revealing uncertainty about her true desire.
- **Emotional Paradox:** Anticipation blends with anxiety, and hope intertwines with fear, creating a complex emotional dynamic.
- **Impact on Perception:** The emotional duality reshapes the protagonist's reality, turning her journey into a leap into the unknown, filled with both exhilaration and dread.

3.2.17 *The Tangible Metaphor*

Description:

Abstract emotions and sensory experiences are intertwined, rendering metaphors physically palpable. Characters experience emotions as though they are tangible, literal realities, making metaphorical concepts part of their immediate perception.

Excerpt from the Novel:

Note: The breaks and shifts in the passage are preserved to reflect the fragmented sensory experience central to the metaphorical interpretation.

The light through the window softens, and I feel it before I see it—the room shifting, but not in any way I can name. It has subtly tightened around me, closing in by just a hair; barely perceptible—the way you notice a breeze, not by its presence, but by the absence of stillness. I blink, slow, and then pause mid-breath, for a moment too small to matter to anyone but me.

“Something entered the space,” I whisper to the Shadow. I don’t need to turn my head to know it. I know. My fingers hover above the arm of the chair, suspended for no reason I can explain. Shadow appears passive, but I can tell it’s curiously attuned to my unease. There’s no sound, no movement. Nothing has changed, yet everything is different. The quiet is... closer now. More deliberate. (...)

The air feels... fragile, delicate, so soft it touches me like skin. (...)

Nothing moves, but the sensation lingers, spreading beneath the surface of my thoughts as an unsettling weightlessness fills the space. (...)

Analysis:

- **Personification of Space:** The room is described as though it is actively pressing in, tightening around the protagonist. The air and light become characters, shifting and exerting subtle influence over her sensations.

- **Sensory Ambiguity:** The character’s perception blurs between the physical and the imagined, as the air feels like *"skin"* and the walls seem to *"lean in."* It creates an ambiguity that makes the intangible atmosphere tangible.
- **Metaphorical Reality:** The abstract feeling of *"closeness"* becomes so intense that it is physically felt, as though the air itself is actively participating in her emotional state.

Category 4: Space, Objects, and Environment

3.2.18 Spatial Emotional Reverberation (*Psychological Echo Spaces*)

Description:

Physical space resonates with the *characters*, reflecting their *psychological state*⁴⁰. The environment takes on the weight of the character's *lived experience*, subtly shifting in response to the emotional tensions present in the narrative.

Excerpt from the Novel:

The room twists and dissolves into scattered visions of a life together—snippets of laughter, and whispers in the dark, and shared silences and... and fingers entwined. The feel of us.

Analysis:

- **Emotional Reflection:** The room mirrors her emotional memories, reinforcing the connection between space and feeling.
- **Internal-External Link:** Spaces reflect the character’s psychological state, intertwining her emotions with the environment.
- **Resonant Atmosphere:** The environment becomes saturated with the emotional undertones of her experience.

⁴⁰ Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*.

3.2.19 Emotional Microcosm

Description:

A small, intimate space encapsulates the character's broader emotional world. Specific objects or environments serve as concentrated symbols of complex emotional experiences⁴¹, transforming tangible items into emotional vessels.

Excerpt from the Novel:

I hug all the pieces I could gather and hold them close to mine, twirling with my memories in this land of nothing right, as I exhale myself onto the pillow that still holds the shape of our dreams.

Analysis:

Symbolic Object: The pillow embodies their shared dreams and relationship, serving as a physical representation of their emotional history.

Condensed Emotions: The entirety of their relationship is encapsulated in this single point, making it a focal point of emotional significance.

Tangible Emotions: Physical objects become a vessel for complex emotional narratives, grounding abstract feelings in something tangible.

3.2.20 Emotional Echolocation

Description:

Characters *experience* their internal world by sending out emotional cues and interpreting the emotional feedback from their environment⁴². Like echolocation, this method allows them to sense their emotional surroundings and reflect on their own internal state.

⁴¹ Sigmund Freud, *The Uncanny* (2003).

⁴² Carl Jung, *Psychological Types* (1921).

Excerpt from the Novel:

In the backdrop, a faint cry; I can't figure out if it's mine or if it's echoing the other half of my broken heart—the one beating in his chest.

Analysis:

- **Emotional Projections:** She embodies the signals, attempting to process her emotions through her surroundings.
- **Echoed Response:** The faint cry becomes a reflection, blurring the line between internal and external grief.
- **Emotional Interpretation:** In receiving and interpreting emotional echoes, she attempts to understand and cope with her feelings.

3.2.21 The Tactile Absence

Description:

Absence is experienced as a physical sensation. The character feels the void not only emotionally but also as a tactile experience, where emptiness becomes something that presses in on her, making absence palpable.

Excerpt from the Novel:

There, at the very edge, bordering on the collapse of reality and the dawn of oblivion, an uncanny stillness pins me down to my bed.

Analysis:

- **Palpable Emptiness:** The stillness physically "*pins*" her down, transforming the absence into a tactile experience.
- **Felt Void:** Emotional emptiness manifests physically, intensifying the sensation of loss.
- **Presence in Absence:** The lack of presence becomes an overwhelming force, emphasizing the weight of what's missing.

3.2.22 *Emotional Entanglement of Objects (Object-Emotion Resonance)*

Description:

Objects in the character's world hold emotional weight, becoming anchors to memories or emotional states. These items resonate with the emotions tied to them, influencing the character's perception of the present.

Excerpt from the Novel:

One last attempt at balance—I clutch onto the cushions, sliding my fingers across the fabric in a graze, rough and familiar, like braille pages of our past, inviting touch to read our history.

Analysis:

- **Emotional Memory:** The cushions act as emotional artifacts, bringing past experiences to the surface.
- **Textural Connection:** The metaphor of the cushions as "*braille pages of our past*" evokes the tactile nature of memory.
- **Emotional Anchor:** Objects carry the emotional weight of past events, grounding the character in both history and feeling.

3.2.23 *Emotional Architecture of Space*

Description:

The physical environment reflects the character's internal state, with the layout and structure of the space itself transforming into emotional mirrors.

Excerpt from the Novel:

The world outside is a stunningly grotesque replica of my inner chaos. Buildings twist and contort under a sky bruised, trapped in a twilight that feels endless, while lights pulse like the heartbeat of a city on the edge.

Analysis:

- **Distorted Reality:** Buildings "*twist and contort*," visually reflecting her emotional distress.
- **Mood Projection:** The "*bruised sky*" and "*endless twilight*" capture the emotional atmosphere, projecting it onto the external world.
- **Inner Turmoil:** The external environment becomes a manifestation of her own mental chaos, the architecture of the space becoming a metaphor for her fractured state.

Category 5: Narrative Structure and Form

3.2.24 Recursive Emotional Structuring (*Fractal Narrative Structure*)

Description:

A central emotional or thematic core fracture into smaller, recursive components. Each iteration reflects the original emotion or theme⁴³, expanding and deepening it as the story progresses in a self-replicating pattern of emotional evolution.

Excerpt from the Novel:

This is reflected in the Emotional Fractal technique.

Analysis:

- **Fractal Patterns:** The core emotional theme is repeated in smaller narratives, creating a self-replicating structure throughout the story.
- **Deepening Emotions:** Each iteration of the theme adds new emotional depth, layering on the original feeling as the narrative advances.

⁴³ Benoit B. Mandelbrot, *The Fractal Geometry of Nature* (1983).

- **Structural Reflection:** The narrative structure mirrors the thought pattern, using recursion to reflect the fractal nature of the character's experience.

3.2.25 *Internal Reverb Effect*

Description:

The repetition of words or phrases between external and internal monologue amplifies emotional resonance⁴⁴. It creates a reverberation effect which heightens the emotional intensity of the character's thoughts, making them echo and resonate throughout their mind.

Excerpt from the Novel:

The protagonist echoes the words "*The pain—The pain. The fear*" as her internal monologue interweaves with the narration, reflecting the amplification of her emotional strain.

Analysis:

- **Repetition:** The repeated words ("*The pain—The pain. The fear.*") intensify the protagonist's emotional turmoil, emphasizing her distress.
- **Emotional Amplification:** Each repetition echoes the emotional state, amplifying the overwhelming sense of fear and pain.
- **Internal Echoes:** The reverberation of the thoughts within the character's mind reflects the cyclical and inescapable nature of her internal conflict.

⁴⁴ Milman Parry and Adam Parry, *The making of Homeric verse : the coll. papers of Milman Parry* (1987).

3.2.26 *The Emotional Fractal*

Description:

An emotional moment splinters into infinite smaller iterations, creating a fractal effect. The recursion expands the emotional complexity of a single event, reflecting and deepening the original feeling across the narrative like a self-replicating emotional pattern.

Excerpt from the Novel:

The mirror tosses back a version of me as if it has been whirled through a cosmic blender, morphing into shapes that don't quite stick. It's not only a reflection staring back but a whole gallery of emotions, imprisoned in a perpetual loop—hope flickers, despair looms, joy bursts, and pain shadows. They all merge into faces I swear I've known, and echoes of a past I carry, recklessly pieced together in a spectacle of what it means to be achingly, beautifully human.

Analysis:

- **Fragmentation:** The mirror represents emotional splintering, where multiple feelings fragment and multiply, each one reflecting a new state of being.
- **Recursive Emotions:** Repeated emotional iterations mirror the fractal effect, looping the protagonist's emotional complexity through recurring experiences.
- **Reflection of Self:** The shattered image symbolizes the fracturing of the protagonist's identity, displaying multiple layers of emotional depth at once.

3.2.27 *Simultaneous Emotional Realities (Multilayered Emotional Concurrency)*

Description:

Characters experience multiple, concurrent emotional states, with contrasting feelings existing simultaneously without a clear resolution, layering a multidimensional emotional experience that transcends linear progression.

Excerpt from the Novel:

*Dazed, deliberate, yet detached—I had no time to get lost. But somehow, I did.
Obviously. But, obviously, I did.*

Analysis:

- **Emotional Duality:** The protagonist feels both deliberate and detached at the same time, exemplifying the coexistence of conflicting emotional states.
- **Repetition for Emphasis:** The repetition of "*Obviously. But, obviously, I did.*" highlights the tension between certainty and confusion.
- **Cognitive Dissonance:** She grapples with conflicting emotions, accepting the dissonance of feeling both in control and lost at once.

Category 6: Meta and Perception Techniques

3.2.28 Metacognitive Perceptual Self-Awareness

Description:

A self-reflexive technique where characters reflect on the act of perceiving.⁴⁵ They question the reliability of their own perception while also inviting the reader into a dialogue about the subjective nature of reality.

⁴⁵ John H. Flavell, "Metacognition and cognitive monitoring: A new area of cognitive-developmental inquiry," (1979).

Excerpt from the Novel:

You're in a dream. Nothing here makes sense. The hallway, the fragments, the comet, the pain—The pain. The fear.

Analysis:

- **Self-Awareness:** The character explicitly recognizes the dream-like quality of their surroundings, acknowledging the unreliability of their perception.
- **Listing Elements:** The fragmented list—hallway, fragments, comet—emphasizes the disjointed, surreal reality the character is experiencing.
- **Emotional Repetition:** The repetition of "*The pain—The pain. The fear.*" intensifies her awareness of her emotional state, layering the perception of the dream.

3.2.29 Progressive Perceptual Dissociation (Perceptual Drift)

Description:

The character's perception gradually shifts away from an externally coherent reality. Internal emotional and psychological states overpower their experience, causing their perception of the outside world to distort in reflection to their inner process⁴⁶.

Excerpt from the Novel:

The world around me feels altered, as if rearranged by an unseen force. There is a sense of upheaval, of landscapes torn apart and pieced back together in a rush, echoing the disarray left in the wake of a sudden, tragic loss

⁴⁶ Bessel Van Der Kolk, *The body keeps the score: Brain, mind, and body in the healing of trauma* (2014).

Analysis:

- **Perceptual Drift:** Reality feels unstable and disjointed, as though the external world has been rearranged to reflect the character's emotional state.
- **Emotional Overpowering:** The character's internal emotional upheaval distorts their perception, overpowering any sense of external coherence.
- **Dissociation:** There is a growing detachment from objective reality, as the character becomes lost in her internal emotional and psychological chaos.

4. Comparative Analysis

Subjective Realism, to be fully understood within the wider landscape of narrative theory, invites a comparative approach. This examination aims to reveal the distinct theoretical space Subjective Realism occupies through its divergence from and alignment with other prominent literary movements, such as Surrealism, Psychological Realism, and Phenomenology.

4.1 *Subjective Realism vs. Surrealism*

Surrealism and Subjective Realism both challenge traditional perceptions of reality, but they diverge fundamentally in their approaches to representing the unconscious and altering reality.

Surrealism

- **Focus on the Subconscious:** It explores the unconscious mind, dreams, and irrational thoughts. It introduces fantastical or bizarre elements that do not adhere to the rules of reality, blending fantasy with realism to create worlds operating outside conventional logic⁴⁷.
- **Disruption of Reality:** Surrealist works intentionally disrupt the reader's sense of reality by juxtaposing illogical or dreamlike scenarios with the ordinary. There is little need to explain or justify these occurrences within the narrative.
- **Key Elements:** Surrealism thrives on absurdity, non-linearity, and the liberation of the unconscious mind, often embracing the fantastical as an ordinary part of existence.

⁴⁷ André Breton, *Manifestoes of Surrealism* (2020).

Subjective Realism

- **Emotionally Grounded Perception:** It remains firmly rooted in the emotional and psychological states of characters. Apparent surreal moments are representations of the protagonist's emotional truth rather than actual disruptions of reality.
- **Perceptual Distortions:** Changes in reality are subtle distortions based on the character's emotions. These may include time slowing down, spaces feeling constricted, or colors becoming more vivid—all reflecting the internal emotional landscape.
- **Key Elements:** The external world remains grounded in realism but is emotionally responsive. Shifts in perception reinterpret reality through the lens of the character's emotional experience.

Key Distinctions

While Surrealism often uses fantastical imagery to explore the subconscious, creating scenarios that break from reality, Subjective Realism retains the rules of the plausible world. It allows emotional perception to subtly bend those rules, creating a reality where emotions influence how it is experienced without abandoning realism.

Example Comparison

- **Surrealism:** A character literally floats into the sky, as a normal occurrence within the story's universe, reflecting a dreamlike escape from reality.
- **Subjective Realism:** A character feels as though they are floating due to emotional disconnection or euphoria. The experience is metaphorical, representing their internal state, and the narrative makes it clear that this is a subjective account rather than a supernatural event.

4.2 Subjective Realism vs. Psychological Realism

Psychological Realism

- **Internal Focus with Stable Reality:** It places focus on characters' thoughts, feelings, and motivations while keeping the external world constant. Interpretations and reactions are influenced by their emotions, but the external events and environment remain unaffected.
- **Interpretation Over Alteration:** Emotions influence how characters interpret events, but they do not alter the events themselves or the sensory perception of reality.
- **Key Elements:** Emphasis on character development, moral dilemmas, and the complexity of human psychology within a stable, objective reality⁴⁸.

Subjective Realism

- **Externalization of Emotions:** It allows emotions to reshape sensory reality. The character's emotional state can cause perceptual changes—such as time dilation, distorted sounds, or shifting spatial dimensions—that reflect their internal experience externally.
- **Perceptual Alteration:** The external world is experienced differently due to the character's emotions, effectively blurring the line between internal feelings and external perception.
- **Key Elements:** The narrative depicts reality as subjectively experienced, with the external environment responsive to the character's emotional state⁴⁹.

⁴⁸ Henry James, *The Portrait of a Lady* (2020).

⁴⁹ Edmund Husserl, *Ideas pertaining to a pure phenomenology and to a phenomenological philosophy* (1983).

Key Distinctions

While Psychological Realism focuses on the internal interpretations within a stable reality, Subjective Realism externalizes emotions, allowing them to modify the character's sensory perception of reality itself.

Example Comparison

- **Psychological Realism:** A character feels anxious and perceives others' neutral actions as threatening, though those actions haven't changed. The external environment remains the same; only the character's interpretation is affected.
- **Subjective Realism:** The same character's anxiety causes the room to feel smaller, lights to flicker, and sounds to amplify. Their sensory experience of the environment is altered, reflecting their internal state.

4.3 Subjective Realism vs. Phenomenology

Phenomenology shares a focus on perception with Subjective Realism, but their approaches to experience and reality differ significantly.

Phenomenology

- **Descriptive Focus:** It aims to describe experiences as they are perceived, setting aside biases and preconceptions to focus on pure perception.
- **Objective Observation:** It emphasizes observing phenomena without altering them, striving for a neutral description of experiences.
- **Key Elements:** Concerned with the structures of consciousness and phenomena as they appear to consciousness, without distorting or interpreting them through an emotional lens.

Subjective Realism

- **Emotionally Influenced Perception:** It embraces emotional distortion as a central element, acknowledging perception as inherently subjective and influenced by emotions, thus allowing internal states to reshape external reality.
- **Active Alteration:** Emotions actively distort sensory experiences, so the character's perception of reality is filtered by their internal emotional state.
- **Key Elements:** Depicts reality as fluid and malleable, contingent upon the character's emotional and psychological state.

Key Distinctions

Phenomenology seeks neutral descriptions of perception, aiming to understand experiences without emotional bias. In contrast, Subjective Realism incorporates emotional biases, demonstrating how they alter the character's sensory experience of the world.

Example Comparison

- **Phenomenology:** A detailed description of a flower as it appears to the observer, focusing on its color, shape, and scent without personal interpretation.
- **Subjective Realism:** The same flower might appear dull or vibrant depending on the character's mood, with its scent evoking memories or emotions that alter the perception of its appearance.

7. Conclusion

Subjective Realism, as explored in this essay, offers a distinct literary framework that elevates emotional experience to a core element in shaping narrative reality. Departing from established models, it structures and defines a grey area in literary fiction, where perception is inherently pliant, recalibrating in response to the character's emotional and psychological states.

The emphasis on perception as a dynamic process opens new avenues for storytelling, where the boundaries between external reality and internal experience dissolve into a seamless whole. This model facilitates emotional experience to actively reshape the narrative, aligning time, space, and sensory input with the character's inner world. In doing so, it offers a deeper, more intimate engagement with human consciousness, making it uniquely positioned to portray the layers of our interactions with reality.

7.1 Literary Innovation and Cultural Resonance

Our collective understanding of the human mind has considerably evolved in the past decades, giving center stage to emotional life in public and personal discourse. Amid this movement, Subjective Realism gains tangible relevance, offering writers the freedom to step beyond the limitations of conventional narrative form, depicting realities that reflect the deeply subjective, often non-linear, nature of human experience. In turn, it welcomes a new level of empathy and psychological depth in narrative fiction by inviting readers to perceive reality through the emotional lenses of its characters.

The potential for genre innovation is significant. Writers across literary and speculative genres can use these techniques to explore non-linear time structures, fragmented realities, and sensory modulations that bring characters' inner lives into vivid focus. Likewise, readers are encouraged

not only to engage with the story on a cognitive level but to experience it on an emotional and perceptual one, further blurring the distinction between the two.

7.2 Methodological Contributions for Writers and Scholars

The narrative techniques underpinning Subjective Realism—such as affective sensory modulation, emotional synesthesia, and temporal elasticity—serve as practical tools for both writers and scholars. They offer a method for portraying the minds of characters in a way that feels both authentic and nuanced, pushing beyond superficial depictions of psychological experience. For creative writers, these tools encourage innovation in form and content, inviting exploration into how internal states govern external perception.

For scholars and students of literature, Subjective Realism offers a rich field of inquiry, connecting narratology, phenomenology, and psychoanalytic theory. Its rejection of an objective, fixed reality aligns with postmodern epistemologies, offering a space of exploration on how literature reflects the fluidity of human experience.

7.3 Final Reflections

Subjective Realism encourages a rethinking of how stories are told, and perhaps more importantly, how they are experienced. It situates perception at the intersection of emotional truth and external reality, challenging readers to reconsider their own assumptions about the nature of reality itself. The framework allows narratives to pulse with psychological and emotional complexity, revealing that reality is not something given, but something continually shaped by the subjective view.

Literary culture is ever more attuned to the complexities of human consciousness and is poised for further evolution. In a broader sense, Subjective Realism is both a technique and a lens through which future versions of perceptual narratives may unfold.

Bibliography

- Bachelard, Gaston. *The Poetics of Space*. 2014.
- Bergson, Henri. *Time and Free Will*. 2014.
- . *Time and Free Will : An Essay on the Immediate Data of Consciousness*. 1910.
- Booth, Wayne C. *The Rhetoric of Fiction*. 1961.
- Bowers, Maggie Ann. *Magic(Al) Realism*. 2004.
- Breton, André. *Manifestoes of Surrealism*. 2020.
- Cohn, Dorrit. *Transparent Minds : Narrative Modes for Presenting Consciousness in Fiction*. 2011.
- Culler, Jonathan D. *Literary Theory: A Very Short Introduction*. 2011.
- Cytowic, Richard E. *The Man Who Tasted Shapes*. 2003.
- Dostoyevsky, Fyodor. *Notes from the Underground*. 2015.
- Flavell, John H. "Metacognition and Cognitive Monitoring: A New Area of Cognitive-Developmental Inquiry." (1979).
- Freud, Sigmund. *On Murder, Mourning and Melancholia - Freud*. 2024.
- . *The Uncanny*. 2003.
- Hazell, Stephen. "Henry James: The Art of Fiction (1884)." 2022.
- Husserl, Edmund. *Ideas Pertaining to a Pure Phenomenology and to a Phenomenological Philosophy*. 1983.
- James, Henry. *The Portrait of a Lady*. 2020.
- Jung, Carl. *Psychological Types*. 1921.
- Laing, R. D. *The Divided Self : An Existential Study in Sanity and Madness*. 1960.
- Lakoff, George, and Mark Johnson. *Metaphors We Live By*. 1980.
- Loftus, Elizabeth F. *Memory, Surprising New Insights into How We Remember and Why We Forget*. 1980.
- Lyotard, Jean-François. *The Postmodern Condition: A Report on Knowledge*. 1984.
- Mandelbrot, Benoit B. *The Fractal Geometry of Nature*. 1983.
- Merleau-Ponty, Maurice. *Phenomenology of Perception*. 2002.
- Panksepp, Jaak. *Affective Neuroscience : The Foundations of Human and Animal Emotions*. 1998.
- Parry, Milman, and Adam Parry. *The Making of Homeric Verse : The Coll. Papers of Milman Parry*. 1987.
- Ricoeur, Paul. *Memory, History, Forgetting*. 2009.
- Sacks, Oliver. *Hallucinations*. 2012.
- Sartre, Jean-Paul. *Being and Nothingness : A Phenomenological Essay on Ontology*. 1999.
- Shklovsky, Viktor. "Art as Technique." (2020).
- Van Der Kolk, Bessel. *The Body Keeps the Score: Brain, Mind, and Body in the Healing of Trauma*. 2014.
- Watt, Ian. *The Rise of the Novel*. 1959.

